

SHERATON GRAND

Bengaluru Whitefield
Hotel & Convention Center

April 19th, 2022

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

This is to certify that **Arjun V** a student of **Srinivas University, Mangalore** has successfully completed his Industrial Training in **Culinary, Food & Beverage, Front Office, & Housekeeping** in our organization from 11th December, 2021 to 18th April, 2022.

During his tenure we found him to be sincere, hardworking and diligent. We wish him success in all his future endeavours.

For Sheraton Grand Bengaluru Whitefield Hotel & Convention Centre

Shashi Prabha
Human Resources Associate

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